

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF 1,3-BENZODIOXOLE DERIVATIVES TO FIND OUT POTENT HISTONE DEACETYLASE-1 (HDAC1) ENZYME INHIBITOR

¹Sonaxi Kharb, ²Ravi Tomar, ³Anshul Singh

^{1,3}Department of Chemistry, Baba Mastnath University, Asthal Bohr, Rohtak, Haryana, India

²Department of Chemistry, SGT University, Gurugram, Haryana, India

E-mail: anshul9008@gmail.com

Corresponding author: Anshul Singh

KEYWORDS

In silico study, molecular docking, HDAC1 inhibitor, 1,3-benzodioxole analogs

ABSTRACT

In modern drug designing, molecular docking is routinely used for understanding drug-receptor interaction. In the present study, eight derivatives containing substituted 1,3-benzodioxole propargyl ether moiety compounds 1-8 were chosen for protein-ligand docking. Compounds were screened for their [anti-cancer activity](#) by inhibition of HDAC1. Compounds 5 and 6 were found to be potent Histone deacetylase enzyme inhibitors. The *in silico* molecular docking study and pharmacological study results showed that these derivatives have minimum binding energy and have a good affinity toward the active pocket, thus, they may be considered good inhibitors of HDAC1.

1. INTRODUCTION

Molecular docking is a computational method for predicting the placement of ligands in the binding sites of their receptor(s) (Yuriev *et al.*, 2015). It consists of the generation of several possible conformations/orientations, i.e., poses, of the ligand within the protein binding site. For this reason, the availability of the three-dimensional structure of the molecular target is a necessary condition (Salmaso and Moro, 2018). Molecular docking aims to accomplish an optimized conformation for both the protein and ligand and the fundamental direction between protein and ligand so that the free energy of the general method is minimized (Dnyandev *et al.*, 2021). The protein-ligand interaction is the most interesting case, because of its applications in medicines. Ligand is a small molecule, which interacts with protein's binding sites. There are

several possible mutual con-formations in which binding may occur. These are commonly called binding modes.

Cancer ranks as a leading cause of death and an important barrier to increasing life expectancy in every country of the world (Bray *et al.*, 2021). According to estimates from the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2019, cancer is the first or second leading cause of death before the age of 70 years in 112 of 183 countries and ranks third or fourth in a further 23 countries. Worldwide, an estimated 19.3 million new cancer cases (18.1 million excluding non melanoma skin cancer) occurred, and almost 10.0 million cancer deaths (9.9 million excluding non melanoma skin cancer) occurred in 2020 (Sung *et al.*, 2021).

Histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors play a crucial role in restoring the balance of acetylation and deacetylation of lysine residues of histones and non-histone proteins, which are applied to treat several diseases including cancer (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). Modification of histones by acetylation plays a key role in epigenetic regulation of gene expression by changing the structure of chromatin and by modulating the accessibility of transcription factors to their target DNA sequences (Eckschlager *et al.*, 2017). Histone acetylation, a well-studied posttranslational histone modification, is controlled by the opposing activities of histone acetyltransferases (HATs) and histone deacetylases (HDACs) (Li and Seto, 2016; Sharma *et al.*, 2010). Tumor cells on exposure to HDACi result in acetylation of histone and activation of gene expression thus enhancing the chance of tumor cells to undergo apoptosis. Apoptosis or programmed cell death appears to be the predominant way of HDACi-induced cell death in cancer therapy (Frew *et al.*, 2009; Shanmugam *et al.*, 2022). In humans, 18 HDAC enzymes are currently known, grouped into four classes based on their homology with yeast. proteins: the Class 1 Rpd3-like proteins, the Class 2 Hda1-like proteins, the Class 3 Sir2-like proteins, and the Class 4 proteins (Bondarev *et al.*, 2021). Classical HDACs display Zn^{2+} dependent deacetylase activity, the binding of HDACi to the Zn^{2+} ion, which resides at the active site of HDACs, interferes with the activity of HDACs,(Li and Seto, 2016).

Thus, the identification of potent and safe HDAC inhibitors is a viable strategy to inhibit cancer cell progression. SAHA, Belinostat, and Romidepsin are the FDA-approved HDAC inhibitors available for treating cancers (Mann *et al.*, 2007; Marks, 2007; Barbarotta and Hurley, 2015). Other than these synthetic inhibitors, few naturally occurring HDAC inhibitors were also reported for treating carcinomas of the breast, prostate and colon, and rectum. The lower efficacy of SAHA in clinical trials, and adverse effects associated with TSA, emphasize the need for the identification of potent HDAC inhibitors with lesser adverse effects. Based on pharmacophore modeling, a good HDACI should have at least three sides/regions: the

attachment site of the Zn²⁺ cofactor/HDAC active site (Zn²⁺ binding group/ZBG), hydrophobic cap (CAP), and linker containing connecting unit (CU) with electronegative groups (Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

The object of the present work was to analyze the interactions involved in the inhibition of HDAC1 by various derivatives of 1,3-benzodioxole and collection of derivatives of the inhibitor that had the greatest affinity, applying the molecular docking method. This is a commonly used computational strategy in structure-based drug design (Ferreira *et al.*, 2015). The intent is to realize a computational absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADME/Tox) (Li, 2001) prediction for exploring the best possible inhibitors for HDAC1. These actions may aid the development of more efficient anti-cancer agents.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Protein preparation

The enzyme selected as a pharmacological target for the work was HDAC, the 3D structure of which was retrieved from the PDB (PDB ID: 4BKX). It has two chains A, and B. In the protein structure preparation, chain A was removed and the co-crystal selective inhibitor ACT was used for active site determination using the BIOVIA DISCOVERY STUDIO tool. The residues His140, His141, Gly149, Phe150, Asp176, His178, Gln260, Asp264, Gly300, Gly301, and Tyr303 were found to be present in the binding pocket of the proposed target enzyme.

2.2 Structure validation of protein

The energy minimized model protein was evaluated by using several programs *viz*, ProCheck (Laskowski *et al.*, 1993), ERRAT, and VERIFY3D (Eisenberg *et al.*, 1997) tools available at the SAVES server (<https://services.mbi.ucla.edu/SAVES/>) (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). ERRAT works by analyzing the statistics of non-bonded interactions between different atom types, with higher scores indicating higher quality. The overall quality score calculated by ProSA (Wiederstein and Sippl, 2007) (<https://prosa.services.came.sbg.ac.at/prosa.php>) for a specific input structure is displayed in a plot that shows the scores of all experimentally determined protein chains currently available in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). PROSA-web Z-scores of all protein chains in PDB are determined by X-ray crystallography (light blue) and NMR spectroscopy (dark blue) concerning their length. The Z-score of protein models was present in the range represented by the large black dot.

2.3 Ligand preparation

The two-dimensional structures of the derivative compounds were drawn in ChemDraw Ultra (Cousins, 2011) and the structure of each compound was analyzed for connection error in bond order. The energy of these derivatives was minimized using ChemDraw3D and saved in .sdf format. The ligands were then further converted into the.pdb format using an open babel tool for molecular docking (O'Boyle *et al.*, 2011).

2.4 In silico molecular docking studies

To carry out the docking simulation, the energy minimized compounds were then read as input .pdb format for AutoDock Vina (Trott and Olson, 2009). Before docking, all the heteroatoms were removed from the 4BKX.pdb. The Graphical User Interface program "AutoDock Tools" was used to prepare, run, and analyze the docking simulations. Polar hydrogens were added followed by the addition of Kollman charges, to the receptor for the preparation of protein in docking simulation. Since ligands are not peptides, the Gasteiger charge was assigned. All atoms were assigned as AD4 type to save the protein .pdbqt format. Grid Dimensions were obtained with the help of Discovery Studio Client. In this study, the binding site was selected based on amino acid residues involved in binding with ACT which would be considered the best accurate active region. Therefore, the grid was centered at the region including all the 12 amino acid residues His140, His141, Gly149, Phe150, Asp176, His178, Gln260, Asp264, Gly300, Gly301, and Tyr303 that surround the active site as in Fig. 2. The grid box size was set at 20, 20, and 20 Å for x, y and z respectively, and the grid center was set to -47.454, 16.109 and -5.068 for x, y and z respectively, which covered all the 12 amino acid residues in the considered active pocket. Docking software AutoDock 4.2 Program supplied with AutoGrid 4.0 and AutoDock 4.0 was used to produce grid maps. The spacing between grid points was 0.375 angstrom. The Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) was chosen to search for the best conformers. Binding residues and different bonds involved in the binding of resulting docked complexes were evaluated using the AutoDock tools interaction determining module and further docked complexes were analyzed using the Chimera molecular modeling tool. (Yang *et al.*, 2012).

2.5 Pharmacokinetic Analysis

Pharmacokinetic properties were predicted by using SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch>) and pkCSM software (<https://biosig.unimelb.edu.au/pkcsml/>) (Daina *et al.*, 2017; Pires *et al.*, 2015).

All potential drugs had to meet Lipinski's Rule of Five (Zhang and Wilkinson, 2007), which states that likely orally active drugs must complete two of these four proprieties:

- no more than 5 hydrogen bond donors;
- no more than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors;
- the molecular weight under 500 g/mol;
- the Log P below 5.

Compounds 5 and 6 didn't violate Lipinski's Rule of Five.

3. RESULT

HDAC-1 enzyme (4BKX) structure (as shown in Figure 1.) was evaluated for its three-dimensional structural properties by using the SAVES server. Ramachandran plot analyzed the stereochemical properties by assessing the phi and psi dihedral angles (Morris *et al.*, 1992). The plot showed that 89.8% of amino acid residues are in the favored region, 10.2% in the allowed region, and 0.0% in the generously allowed region as shown in Figure 2. The overall quality score of the structure calculated by the ERRAT web interface was found to be 93.906. Red bars identify the misfolded region located distantly from the active site, yellow bars demonstrate the error region between 95% and 99%, and white bars indicate the region with a lower error rate for protein folding. It is shown in Figure 3. In the Verify 3D analysis, it was found that none of the amino acids had a negative score. Therefore, the predicted models were compatible with its amino acid sequence (Elengoe *et al.*, 2014). This web interface also confirms the good quality of HDAC-1 protein structure with more than 80% amino acids consisting of 3D-1D profiles (Figure 4). ProSA score came out to be a Z-score of -10.7, as shown in Figure 5, suggesting that the HDAC-1 structure Z-score is within the range of scores of native protein structures of similar size. The good quality of protein was confirmed by these tools.

Study the interactions involved in the inhibition of HDAC by various compounds to identify new inhibitors of HDAC1. The results of the molecular docking by AutoDock Vina of these inhibitors are represented below in Table 1. The results presented in Table 1 reveal that among the 8 docked inhibitors, compound 5 and compound 6 demonstrated the highest score of -7.0 and -6.9 KJ/mol respectively Figure 6, and hence, the most potent inhibitors of HDAC1. The potent interaction is shown in Figure 7(a,b). Among these compounds, SAHA and TSA were taken as a reference model to interpret the diverse established links with the protein in question, and as starting structures for the development of new potent inhibitors. The resulting docked

complexes were further analyzed with the plip server (Adasme *et al.*, 2021) to identify the involved hydrophobic interactions between designed compounds. The presented docking study reveals that compound 5 fits favorably into the HDAC1 binding pocket as it shows hydrophobic interactions with Arg9, Asp130, Leu293, and Pro294 and hydrogen bonding with Arg8. Compound 6 shows hydrophobic interactions with Tyr23, and His33 as well as hydrogen bonding with Ile305, Arg306, and Tyr336 (Figure 8).

After the evaluation of lead compounds 5 and 6 with *in silico* assays, pharmacological properties were analyzed by SwissADME and pkCSM web interfaces. The results obtained are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Hence, we propose that these two compounds can interact efficiently with the enzyme. Further work was then undertaken to elucidate the mechanism of interaction of these proposed compounds.

4. CONCLUSION

The molecular docking studies of the derivatives were carried out, and such studies' results were reported. *In silico* studies revealed that compound 5 and compound 6 have relatively lesser binding energy than the standard drug and may be considered a good inhibitor of HDAC1. Hence this study has widened the scope of developing these derivatives as promising [anticancer agents](#).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank Dr. Neeraj Kumar for their invaluable assistance in finding out the potent anticancer agent.

REFERENCES

Adasme, M.F., Linnemann, K.L., Bolz, S.N., *et al.* (2021) PLIP 2021: Expanding the scope of the protein-ligand interaction profiler to DNA and RNA. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 49. pp. W530-W534.

Barbarotta, L. and Hurley, K. (2015) Romidepsin for the Treatment of Peripheral T-Cell Lymphoma. *Journal of the Advanced Practitioner in Oncology*. 6. pp. 22–36.

- Bondarev, A.D., Attwood, M.M., Jonsson, J. *et al.* (2021) Recent developments of HDAC inhibitors: Emerging indications and novel molecules. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 87 (12) pp. 4577–4597.
- Bray, F., Laversanne, M., Weiderpass, E. *et al.* (2021) The ever-increasing importance of cancer as a leading cause of premature death worldwide. *Cancer*, 127 (16). pp. 3029–3030.
- Cousins, K.R. (2011) Computer review of ChemDraw ultra12.0. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 133 (21).
- Daina, A., Michielin, O., and Zoete, V. (2017) SwissADME: A free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small molecules. *Scientific Reports*, 7.
- Dnyandev, K.M., Babasaheb, G.V., Chandrashekhar, K.V. *et al.* (2021) A Review on Molecular Docking. *International Research Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, pp. 60–68.
- Eckschlager, T., Plch, J., Stiborova, M. *et al.* (2017) Histone deacetylase inhibitors as anticancer drugs. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 18 (7).
- Eisenberg, D., Lüthy, R. and Bowie, J.U. (1997) VERIFY3D: Assessment of protein models with three-dimensional profiles. *Methods in Enzymology*, 277. pp. 396–404.
- Elengoe, A., Abu Naser, M. and Hamdan, S. (2014) Modeling and docking studies on novel mutants (K71L and T204V) of the ATPase domain of human heat shock 70 kDa protein 1. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 15 (4). pp. 6797–6814.
- Ferreira, L.G., dos Santos, R.N., Oliva, G. *et al.* (2015) Molecular docking and structure-based drug design strategies. *Molecules*. 20 (7). pp. 13384–13421.
- Frew, A.J., Johnstone, R.W. and Bolden, J.E. (2009) Enhancing the apoptotic and therapeutic effects of HDAC inhibitors. *Cancer Letters*. 280 (2). pp. 125–133.
- Kumar, N., Tomar, R., Pandey, A. *et al.* (2018) Preclinical evaluation and molecular docking of 1,3-benzodioxole propargyl ether derivatives as a novel inhibitor for combating the histone deacetylase enzyme in cancer. *Artificial Cells, Nanomedicine and Biotechnology*, 46 (6). pp. 1288–1299.

- Laskowski, R.A., MacArthur, M.W., Moss, D.S. *et al.* (1993) PROCHECK: a program to check the stereochemical quality of protein structures. *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, 26 (2) pp. 283-291.
- Li, A.P. (2001) Screening for human ADME/Tox drug properties in drug discovery. *Drug Discovery Today*. 6 (7). pp. 357-366.
- Li, Y. and Seto, E. (2016) HDACs and HDAC inhibitors in cancer development and therapy. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 6 (10).
- Mann, B.S., Johnson, J.R., He, K. *et al.* (2007) Vorinostat for treatment of cutaneous manifestations of advanced primary cutaneous T-cell lymphoma. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 13 (8) pp. 2318–2322.
- Marks, P.A. (2007) Discovery and development of SAHA as an anticancer agent. *Oncogene*. 26 (9) pp. 1351-1356.
- Morris, A.L., MacArthur, M.W., Hutchinson, E.G. *et al.* (1992) Stereochemical quality of protein structure coordinates. *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics*, 12 (4). pp. 345–364.
- O’Boyle, N.M., Banck, M., James, C.A. *et al.* (2011) Open Babel: An Open chemical toolbox. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 3 (10).
- Pires, D.E.V., Blundell, T.L. and Ascher, D.B. (2015) pkCSM: Predicting small-molecule pharmacokinetic and toxicity properties using graph-based signatures. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 58 (9).
- Salmaso, V. and Moro, S. (2018) Bridging molecular docking to molecular dynamics in exploring ligand-protein recognition process: An overview. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 9:923.
- Shanmugam, G., Rakshit, S. and Sarkar, K. (2022) HDAC inhibitors: Targets for tumor therapy, immune modulation, and lung diseases. *Translational Oncology*. 16.
- Sharma, K., Morla, S., Goyal, A. *et al.* (2020) Computational guided drug repurposing for targeting 2'-O-ribose methyltransferase of SARS-CoV-2. *Life Sciences*, 259.
- Sharma, P., Kumar, S. and Kundu, G.C. (2010) *Transcriptional regulation of human osteopontin promoter by histone deacetylase inhibitor, trichostatin A in cervical cancer cells.*

Sung, H., Ferlay, J., Siegel, R.L. *et al.* (2021) Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 71 (3): 209–249.

Trott, O. and Olson, A.J. (2009) AutoDock Vina: Improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, p. NA-
Wiederstein, M. and Sippl, M.J. (2007) ProSA-web: Interactive web service for the recognition of errors in three-dimensional structures of proteins. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 35. W407-W410.

Yang, Z., Lasker, K., Schneidman-Duhovny, D. *et al.* (2012) UCSF Chimera, MODELLER, and IMP: An integrated modeling system. *Journal of Structural Biology*, 179 (3).

Yuriev, E., Holien, J. and Ramsland, P.A. (2015) Improvements, trends, and new ideas in molecular docking: 2012-2013 in review. *Journal of Molecular Recognition*. 28 (10). pp. 581-604.

Zhang, M.Q. and Wilkinson, B. (2007) Drug discovery beyond the ‘rule-of-five.’ *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 18 (6): 478–488.

Zhao, C., Dong, H., Xu, Q., *et al.* (2020) Histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors in cancer: a patent review (2017-present). *Expert Opinion on Therapeutic Patents*, 30 (4): 263–274.

FIGURES

Figure 1 and 2. Three-dimensional structure of histone deacetylase -1 enzyme and the Ramachandran plot of the HDAC-1 enzyme shows that structure lies within the favored and allowed region.

Figure 3. The overall quality score of the structure calculated by the ERRAT web interface was found to be 93.906. The red bar identifies the misfolded region located distantly from the active site, yellow bars demonstrate the error region between 95% and 99%, and white bars indicate the region with a lower error rate for protein folding.

Figure 4. Verify 3D analysis of Histone deacetylase -1 enzyme showing that none of the amino

acids had a negative score. 98.92% of the residues have averaged 3D-1D score ≥ 0.2

Figure 5. ProSA-web interfaces analysis depiction of HDAC-1 protein structure with NMR/X-ray plot of known structures. The results are generated to display the Z-scores which indicate the overall model quality and energy plots which indicate the local model quality. PROSA-web Z-scores of all protein chains in PDB are determined by X-ray crystallography (light blue) and NMR spectroscopy (dark blue) concerning their length. The Z-score of protein models was present in the range represented by the large black dot.

Figure 6. Binding interactions of compound 5 and compound 6 are shown by the Autodock tool.

Figure 7. Docking results of Compound 5 (magenta colored) and Compound 6 (yellow) were

observed in the Chimera tool.

Figure 8. Hydrophobic interactions (dashed line) and hydrogen bonding (solid blue line) of compound 5 and compound 6 were observed using the PLIP server.

TABLES

Table 1: Molecular binding free energy scores of designed compounds with the receptor HDAC-1 enzyme, using the AutoDock Vina

S.N	Ligand	IUPAC names	Compound Structure	AutoDock na Score (J/mol)
1	Compound 1	6-(3-((4-bromobenzyl)oxy)prop-1-yn-1-yl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxole-5-carbaldehyde		-6.1
2	Compound 2	6-(3-((4-fluorobenzyl)oxy)prop-1-yn-1-yl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxole-5-carbaldehyde		-6.7
3	Compound 3	6-(3-((4-iodobenzyl)oxy)prop-1-yn-1-yl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxole-5-carbaldehyde		-6.1

4	Compound 4	6-(3-((4-methylbenzyl)oxy)prop-1-yn-1-yl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxole-5-carbaldehyde		-6.5
5	Compound 5	4-(((3-(6-formylbenzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)oxy)methyl)phenyl trifluoromethanesulfonate		-7.0
6	Compound 6	6-(3-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethoxy)prop-1-yn-1-yl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxole-5-carbaldehyde		-6.9

Table 2: pharmacological properties were analyzed by SwissADME.

Properties	SAHA	TSA	Compound 7	Compound 8
iLog P	1.84	2.21	3.11	3.44
Heavy atoms	19	22	30	25
Molecular Weight	264	302	442	338
H-bond acceptors	3	3	10	6
H-bond donors	3	2	0	0
Lipinski violations	0	0	0	0
Rotatable bonds	10	7	7	4
Solubility	-3.13	-3.87	-5.2	-3.52

Table 3: pharmacological properties were analyzed by pkCSM.

Parameters	Compound 7	Compound 8
Water solubility (log mol/L)	-4.39	-4.47
Intestinal absorption (%)	95.96	97.51
Skin permeability (log Kp)	-2.73	-2.72
P-glycoprotein substrate	No	No
BBB permeability (log BB)	-1.54	-0.237
Renal OCT2 substrate	No	No
Max. tolerated dose (human) (log mg/kg/day)	0.739	0.355
Oral Rat Acute Toxicity (mol/kg)	2.46	2.62
Oral Rat Chronic Toxicity (log mg/kg_bw/day)	1.085	1.631
Skin Sensitisation	No	No